

ON THE WAY TO FUNCTIONAL COATINGS: POLYELECTROLYTE MULTILAYERS

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SUMMARY

Multilayers formed by the alternate deposition of materials of materials with charges of opposite signs have become of paramount importance for building functional coatings. In the present work we discuss the kinetics of the adsorption of polyelectrolytes onto charged surfaces using dissipative quartz crystal balance and ellipsometry techniques. The effect of the ionic strength and of the charge density of the polymer on the thickness of the multilayer per adsorbed layer is discussed. The water content of the polymer film and the components of the shear modulus have been measured as a function of the thickness and of the ionic strength. Finally, the response of the multilayer to external perturbations, such as the change of salt concentration, is discussed.

Keywords: coating, multilayers, mechanical properties, ellipsometry, D-QCM

INTRODUCTION

From the pioneering work of Decher et al. [1, 2], the sequential electrostatic self-assembly of oppositely charged materials has attracted considerable attention as a simple and versatile method for constructing nanostructured materials. The reason of this interest is the existence of a large amount of promising applications in different fields such as contact lenses, conductive layers, permselective membranes, sensors, light-emitting thin films, electrochromic films and non-linear optical devices. Even though much has been advanced in the understanding of self-assembled multilayers of polyelectrolytes, less effort has been dedicated to the study of the adsorption kinetics and mechanical properties of these systems, and many questions remain open about the detailed structure of this non-equilibrium materials.

EXPERIMENTAL

Several charged blocks had been studied in the building of films by the electrostatic layer-by-layer assembly method. The most widely system studied in our experiments was the multilayer built for poly(diallyldimethylammonium) chloride, PDADMAC, as

positive block, and the sodium salt of poly(4-styrene sulfonate), PSS, as negative block. This system, (PDADMAC+PSS)_n, is a typical example of a multilayer between two strong polyelectrolyte where the role of the electrostatic interaction is essential.

Other kind of systems of great interest in the field of polymer multilayer are the systems where the density of the charge may be tuned by changing the concentration of a charge block and a uncharged block. To this end we have used amphiphilic block copolymers as positive blocks. We have chosen a triblock copolymer of 2-(N,N-dimethylamino)ethyl-methacrylate (charge part), and ε-caprolactone (uncharged part). PDMAEMA copolymers[3], was used with 90, 80 and 70 percent of charge monomers have been used.

Figure 1 Schematic representation of the polymer used in the building of multilayers.

Biocompatible coatings are important for cosmetic and pharmaceutical applications. We have studied the multilayer formed by Chitosan, CHI, as positive block and poly(acrylic acid), PAA, as polyanion.

Figure 1 shows the structure of the different polymers used in this work.

The studies were made by the using a combination of different techniques as D-QCM, ellipsometry, AFM, XPS and neutron and x-ray reflectometry.

RESULTS

Growing process

The growing of the multilayers can be controlled by changes on the assembling conditions that modify the interactions involved in the construction of the films; and these changes lead to modifications on the structure and properties of the multilayers. Two growing regimes have been described in the polyelectrolyte multilayers. In the first case the relationship between the thickness of the multilayer and the number of layer is

almost linear (linear growth). The other one refers to the case in which the change of thickness with the number of layer is faster than linear (the so called exponential growth).

Figure 2 shows some examples of the results found in this work. While (PDADMAC+PSS)_n switches from linear to exponential as a function of the ionic strength, exponential and linear regimes were found for (CHI+PAA)_n and (PDMAEMA+PSS)_n, respectively.

Figure 2 Dependence of the thickness of the multilayer with the number of layer, N . a) Multilayer of PDADMAC and PSS built with different concentration of NaCl. Notice the change from linear to exponential growth mechanism as a consequence of the ionic strength changes[4]. b) Multilayer of CHI and PAA built at different pH conditions.

Exponential growth is found at all pH's, growth in a exponential way in all the examples. c) Multilayer of PDMAEMA and PSS built using different concentration of copolymer. All the film grow linearly.

Ionic strength effect on the assembling

The shift of the ionic strength of the assembling solution produces important effect in the multilayer growth. The increasing of the ionic strength of the polyelectrolyte solution produces the change from an extended conformation to an coiled conformation. This produces an increase of the thickness of polyelectrolyte multilayers. An example is shown in Figure 2.a. In addition to the polymer conformation this effect has been associated to the internal reorganization of the polymer chains in the film. More specifically the partial compensation of polymer charges by salt counterions at high ionic strength makes possible the polymer chains to diffuse to the surface of the film, thus increasing the number of polymer chains adsorbed in each step.

Effect of density of charge on the assembling

When the density of charge of the adsorbing polymer is modified, the adsorbed quantity changes. Even though at first sight it might be counterintuitive, decrease of the charge density of charge of the PDMAEMA copolymers increases the adsorption of the material (see Figure 3). This is a consequence of the increase of the number of loops and tails protruding into the solution. This is accompanied by a change from intrinsic charge compensation mechanism to an extrinsic one.

Figure 3 Effect of the density of charge of PDMAEMA in the bilayer thickness for a multilayer of (PDMAEMA+PSS)_n.

Adsorption kinetics

The adsorption kinetics of the layers in polymer multilayers has been found to be a bimodal process. The first fast adsorption step is related to the diffusion of chains to the surface and a fast mass deposition. The second slower process is related to the internal reorganization of the polymer chains in the multilayer [5]. This kind of kinetics may be modelled in a way similar to that used in the polymer crystallization, for this purpose we have used the Avrami's model. Therefore, the adsorbed amount Γ is given by

$$\Gamma = A \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_1}\right) \right] + B \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_2}\right) \right]^m$$

where Γ represents the adsorbed mass density in the experiments, A and B are the amplitude of the two process and τ_1 and τ_2 are the times of the two different processes. The exponent m was found to be unity for all experiments performed in this work. Thus, by setting $m = 1$, and by introducing the surface concentration in the limit of

equilibrium as $\Gamma_{\infty} = A+B$, we have fitted all the experimental results. Figure 4 shows a typical result for the $(\text{PDADMAC}+\text{PSS})_n$ multilayer.

Figure 4 Two exponential fit of the adsorption kinetic (inset of figure a) in a multilayer of $(\text{PDADMAC}+\text{PSS})_n$. a) Plot of the logarithm of $(\Gamma_{\infty} - \Gamma)$ vs. time, where Γ_{∞} represents the surface concentration at the equilibrium, after long adsorption times where the fastest exponential becomes negligible, it can be fitted to a straight line (solid line). b) Short time behavior of the absorption kinetics, a plot of $\ln(\Gamma_{\infty} - \Gamma - A_2 e^{-t/\tau_2})$ vs. time gives a straight line (solid lines). The parameters obtained from the data shown are: $A_1=4.6 \pm 0.1$, $A_2=5.0 \pm 0.1$, $\tau_1=164 \pm 6s$ and $\tau_2=1450 \pm 25s$.

The two steps kinetics are typical for all the polyelectrolyte multilayers studied, however the behaviour of the kinetic times depends on the system and the growing mechanism of the multilayers.

Figure 5 Dependence of the two adsorption time of the adsorption kinetics on the number of layers. a) Example of a multilayer of $(\text{PDADMAC}+\text{PSS})_n$ built with a concentration of NaCl of 100mM. b) Example of a multilayer of $(\text{PDMAEMA}+\text{PSS})_n$.

When the multilayer grows in an exponentially way, the adsorption times depend on the number of layers, this kind of behaviour is related to the existence of processes of internal reorganization in the multilayer. However for linear growth multilayers the characteristic times do no show any kind of dependence on the layer number, are almost reproducible in all the layers (see Figure 5).

Charge Overcompensation

The driving force of the polyelectrolyte multilayer assembling is the charge overcompensation at the surface of the multilayer, this may be observed for the measurement of the surface potential of the multilayer (see Figure 6). However, the multilayer must be electrically neutral from a macroscopic point of view (at a length scale beyond the Debye length). The electrical neutrality can be achieved by two different mechanisms. In the so-called intrinsic compensation mechanism, the charges carried by an adsorbed polyion are compensated by charges of the polyion adsorbed in the next layer. While in the so-called extrinsic mechanism, part of the charges are compensated by counterions.

Figure 6 Change of the Surface potential with the number of layers for a multilayer of $(\text{PDADMAC}+\text{PSS})_n$ build with a concentration of NaCl of 50 mM.

The compensation mechanism is dependent of the system studied and it is related with the growth mechanism of the multilayer. In the $(\text{PDADMAC}+\text{PSS})_n$ system, the change from linear to exponential growth regimes (Figure 2.a) is accompanied by a change from intrinsic to extrinsic compensation. Similar conclusions can be reached at for $(\text{PDMAEMA}+\text{PSS})_n$ as the charge density is decreased (Figure 3).

Water content

Polyelectrolyte multilayers are highly hydrated. The water content depends on the ionic strength and on the film thickness. Table 1 summarizes the mole fraction of water for one of the multilayers studied.

Table 1 Water Content dependence with the assembling conditions of the (PDADMAC+PSS)_n multilayers.

[NaCl]/mM	X _w (5 Bilayers)	X _w (10 Bilayers)	X _w (15 Bilayers)
50	0.4	0.3	0.2
100	0.5	0.3	0.2
300	0.6	0.4	0.4
500	0.5	0.5	----

Mechanical Properties

Figure 7 shows that the values of the components of the complex shear modulus, G' and G'', of the multilayers are in the range of MPa range, which correspond to the rubbery region of typical polymers [4].

Figure 7 Mechanical properties of multilayers of (PDADMAC-PSS)_n build with different ionic strength a) G' vs h_{ac} . b) G'' vs h_{ac} .

The increase on the ionic strength of the multilayer leads to the multilayer to a gel-like state that it is a consequence of the high hydration degree mentioned above. This gel-like structure are in accordance with the highly mobility of the chains (exponential

growth mechanism, internal reorganization) that it is present in polyelectrolyte multilayer at high ionic strength.

Osmotic response

The polyelectrolyte multilayers respond to the change of ionic strength conditions of the surrounding medium. This is illustrated in Figure 8. The reduction of the ionic strength swells the multilayer in order to obtain an osmotic equilibrium state. The increase of the ionic strength produces the shrinking of the multilayers. In spite of the existence of a hysteresis cycle, this kind of processes were found to be reversible.

Figure 8 Osmotically induce swelling-shrinking process in polyelectrolyte multilayers. Δh_{op} is the change of the thickness as measured by ellipsometry.

CONCLUSIONS

The kinetics of polyelectrolyte adsorption in polymer multilayers have been found to be bimodal. The first process is related to the diffusion of the polymer chains, and the second one to the polymer reorganization in the film. The growth regime is found to depend on ionic strength, and on the nature of the polymer chains. The multilayers have been found to be strongly hydrated, leading to mechanical properties typical of a gelly material.

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